

*Direct approach for experimental
determination of mixed-mode cohesive
laws of composites with large-scale
fibre bridging*

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Overview

Motivation

Derivation of cohesive law

Experimental Characterisation

Results

Concluding remarks

Questions & discussion

Why is it important to measure cohesive laws?

1. While the implementation of cohesive zone models is increasing rapidly, research in determining cohesive law of composites has stalled.

Why is it important to measure cohesive laws?

1. Idealised cohesive laws have several shortcomings

1. For bi-linear cohesive laws, the traction separation law is fully determined by the combined work of the peak traction and a critical opening. Then the shape (and peak traction) are predefined
2. Difficult or not possible to recover R-curves from pre-defined/idealised cohesive laws

2. The shape of the cohesive traction conveys important information of the fracture behaviour of a material such as failure mechanisms, the coupling between tractions, and crack growth stability among other

DTU Derivation of cohesive law

Definition of end-openings and phase angle

End-opening

$$\delta^* = \sqrt{\delta_n^* + \delta_t^*}$$

● crack tip

● fibre bridging region

↑ Normal tractions
→ Shear tractions

Phase angle of end-openings

$$\varphi^* = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\delta_t^*}{\delta_n^*} \right)$$

Phase angle of stress intensity factors

$$\Psi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{K_{II}}{K_I} \right)$$

DTU Derivation of cohesive law

Piece-wise, cylindrical potential function

- The potential function is defined in a piece-wise function:

$$\Phi(\delta, \varphi) = \begin{cases} \Phi_{CT}(\delta, \varphi), & 0 < \delta^* \leq \delta_0 \\ \Phi_B(\delta, \varphi), & \delta_0 < \delta^* \leq \delta_{ss} \end{cases}$$

$$\Phi_{CT}(\delta^*, \varphi^*) = C_4 \delta^{*4} + C_3 \delta^{*3} + C_2 \delta^{*2} + C_1 \delta^* + C_0$$

$$\Phi_B(\delta^*, \varphi^*) = \Phi_0 + (\Phi_{ss} - \Phi_0) \left(\frac{\delta^* - \delta_0}{\delta_{ss}} \right)^\zeta$$

- Parameters:

$$\Phi_0(\varphi), \Phi_{ss}(\varphi), \delta_0(\varphi), \delta_{ss}(\varphi), \zeta(\varphi)$$

Experimental characterisation

Specimens and test groups

- Lay-up: 20 UD-layers (backing facing downwards on all layers – Not symmetrical)
- Fabric type: UD= E-E-1182 Saertex
- Matrix: Epoxy Hexion RIMR 035c / RIMH 037 100/28
- Curing procedure: 12h@40C+10h@80C
- VF of 55%

DCB specimen geometry

Table 2: Elastic properties of UD glass/epoxy laminate

Prop.	value	Unit
E_1	46.3	GPa
ν_{12}	0.26	-
E_2	12.92	GPa
G_{12}	4.3	GPa

Table 3: Geometric properties of standard DCB specimen

Prop.	value	Unit
a_0	70	mm
L	500	mm
B	30	mm
$2H$	20	layers
	~17	mm

Experimental setup

Double cantilever beam under uneven bending moments DCB-UBM

Test set-up

Experimental characterisation

Specimens and test groups

Table 1: List of different mixed-mode tests

M_1/M_2 [-]	φ^* [Deg.]	Ψ [Deg.]
-1.00	0.0 +/- 0.0	0
-0.66	2.7 +/- 1.1	13.6
-0.41	4.9 +/- 0.7	26.8
0.00	8.8 +/- 3.0	50
0.12	9.9 +/- 0.1	56.6
0.50	23.5 +/- 2.8	74.4
0.805	43.5 +/- 13.1	86.7
0.87	50.6 +/- 5.2	89.3
0.96	64.9 +/- 2.8	89.7

Nominal mode I ($M_1 = -M_2$)

Nominal mode II ($M_1 = M_2$)

Experimental characterisation

Data processing

Fracture resistance using J-integral:

$$J_R = \frac{21(M_1^2 + M_2^2) - 6M_1M_2}{4B^2H^3E^*}$$

Normal and tangential end-openings

Figures from Sørensen and Jacobsen 2009

$$\delta_n^* = (H + \Delta_E)\sin\theta_5 - H \cdot \cos\theta_4$$

$$\delta_t^* = (H + \Delta_E)\cos\theta_5$$

DTU Experimental characterisation

Extraction of parameters: Phase angle of openings

Figures adapted from Erives R. 2023

DTU Experimental characterisation

Extraction of parameters

Figures adapted from Erives R., et al 2023

DTU Experimental characterisation

Interpolation of onset parameters: J_0 and δ_0

Figures adapted from Erives R. et al 2023

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Interpolation of parameters at steady-state: J_{SS} and δ_{SS}

Figures adapted from Erives R. et al 2023

DTU Experimental characterisation

Interpolation of shape parameter: ζ

Figures adapted from Erives R. et al 2023

DTU Experimental characterisation

Fitting of fracture resistance

Figures adapted from Erives R. et al 2023

Non-zero normal traction for $\delta_n = 0$
 Negative normal traction for large φ

Figures adapted from Erives R. et al 2023

Results

Peak traction at the crack tip and at bridging region

Relationship between external and local phase angle

Concluding remarks

1. A framework to extract cohesive laws of composites under large scale fiber bridging is presented
2. Extracted cohesive laws depend on physical parameters directly extracted from experimental R-curves, thus ensuing extracted cohesive laws conform to R-curve behavior
3. The measured cohesive laws resulted on fully coupled normal and shear tractions
4. In general, non-monotonic variation of fracture resistance and cohesive tractions can be observed for a fixed opening value

Questions & Discussion